

ROLE OF MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: Materials development is a critical process of facilitating language learning process by mainly coursebooks, audio and video resources. It includes the production, assessment and adaptation of materials intended to enable language acquisition and development. It is also a field of academic study investigating the principles and procedures of the designing, projecting, writing, application, progress and examination of learning materials.

Key words: Materials Development, learning a second language, teaching, coursebooks, YouTube content, videos, promote language learning, diversity, outcome, classroom, long- and short-term motivation, attractive presentation, appealing content, attitudes, factors, authenticity.

Materials Development is a quite new and blossoming field in English Language Teaching which in the past considered to be a part of Methodology. There are several factors contributing to the huge necessity of development of this newly emerged field. They can be:

- Learning languages by different age groups of people
- New technologies which serve to the betterment of the lessons
- New methods and approaches to teaching
- Modified teaching perspectives

English is becoming more and more widespread throughout the globe due to economic, political and educational reasons. At the same time, technology is progressing lightspeed transferring learning process from doing overwhelmingly long queue of repeated monotonous tasks to productive and engaging procedure of computerized activities. It is also creating new opportunities and facilities to ease the

toiling of language learning. YouTube contents, podcasts, educational sites and applications can be example.

The term ‘language-learning materials’ is usually known as coursebooks because main experience of using materials in classrooms is related to printed hand outs and books. Nevertheless, it should be used to refer to anything which is used by teachers or learners to empower the studying of a language. Materials can apparently be podcasts, dictionaries, emails, advertisements, TV commercials, YouTube content, videos, movies, songs, newspapers, food packages, photographs, live talks by invited native speakers, travel guides, medical prescriptions, instructions given by a teacher, tasks written on cards or discussions between learners etc.

‘Materials development is both a field of study and a practical undertaking. As a field it studies the principles and procedures of the design, implementation and evaluation of language teaching materials’ (Tomlinson 2001: 66).

As a practical undertaking it refers to anything which is done by writers, teachers or learners to provide sources of language input, to exploit those sources in ways which maximize the likelihood of intake and to stimulate purposeful output: in other words, the supplying of information about and/or experience of the language in ways designed to promote language learning. Ideally the ‘two aspects of materials development are interactive in that the theoretical studies inform and are informed by the development and use of classroom materials’ (Tomlinson 2001: 66).

Goals of using materials in the language learning process are to achieve effectiveness and long-lasting impact, make the procedure comprehensible, make the mutual learning and teaching process mobile. Effect is achieved when materials have a noticeable outcome on learners, that is when the learners’ interest, concentration and attention are involved. If this is accomplished, there is a better chance that some of the language in the materials will be taken in for processing.

Materials can achieve impact through:

- innovation (unfamiliar topics, illustrations and activities).
- diversity (breaking up the monotony of a unit routine with an unexpected activity; using many different text-types taken from many different types of sources).

- attractive presentation (use of eye-catching colors, 3D styles, special effects, lots of white space; use of photographs)
- appealing content (topics should be suitable and interesting to the target group; engaging stories; universal themes; local references).
- analysis (tasks should be aimed to develop the learners critical thinking).

Numerous scholars have written about the value of learning activities that require the learners to make discoveries for themselves. For example, Rutherford and Sharwood-Smith (1988) emphasize that the role of the classroom and of teaching materials is to aid the learner to make efficient use of the resources to facilitate self-discovery. Similar views are expressed by Bolitho and Tomlinson (1995) and Wright and Bolitho (1993).

Students profit most if they invest curiosity, determination and consideration in the learning activity. Materials can help them to achieve this by providing them with choices of focus and activity, by giving them topic control and by engaging them in learner-centered activities.

Materials should consider that learners differ in affective attitudes the learner's motives, emotions, and attitudes screen what is presented in the language classroom. This affective screening is highly individual and results in different learning rates and results. (Dulay, Burt and Krashen 1982)

Learners should have robust and consistent motivation and they should also be encouraged towards the target language, their teachers and the materials they are being offered. But, of course, ideal learners do not exist and even if they did exist one day, they would no longer be ideal learners the next day. Every learner is unique in their own way by their intrinsic or extrinsic motivation to learn, learning styles (visual, auditory, kinesthetic etc.), special needs and reasons to learn the language. Apparently, there is no possibility of creating one universally acceptable and perfectly matching material for global classrooms and no materials developer can cater for all these affective variables, but it is important for anybody who is writing learning materials to be aware of the inevitable attitudinal differences of the users of the materials.

One obvious implication for the materials developer is ‘to diversify language instruction as much as possible based upon the variety of cognitive styles’ (Larsen-Freeman and Long 1991) and the variety of affective attitudes likely to be found amongst a typical class of learners. Ways of doing this include:

- types of text should be diverse
- activities should not be monotonous and repeated each unit
- extra tasks should be provided for the more positive and motivated learners
- providing variability
- researching and catering for the diverse interests of the identified target learners
- being aware of the cultural sensitivities of the target learners

One of the most important criteria for materials aimed at using in classroom is that they should be authentic. Several scientists have related data from sources of authentic language use with data from coursebooks and have been critical of the lack of authentic texts in the coursebooks, for example, Cullen and Kuo (2007), Lam (2010) and Timmis (2010). Tomlinson (2010b) compares data indicating how people typically get others to help them do something (e.g. by using “If you can ...”) with data showing how textbooks usually teach learners to do this (e.g. by using the imperative). The sources provided in coursebooks are often far from real life usage of the language. The concern there should be to prepare the learner to use the language naturally in real life context.

A lot of linguists have shown data investigating the resemblances between language used in movies and cartoons with that used in ‘natural’ data. For example, Tatsuki (2006) presented data from numerous sources showing many similarities in use between the pragmatic use of language in films and language in ‘natural’ data. Learners can benefit from videos to grasp the language because real accent, pronunciation, manner of everyday natural usage of language. Authenticity is in paramount importance when it comes to language learning.

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